

Spinal versus General Anesthesia for Transabdominal Preperitoneal (TAPP) Repair of Inguinal Hernia: Interim Analysis of A Controlled Randomized Trial

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Abstract:

This randomised controlled research compared spinal and general anaesthesia in 66 patients undergoing Transabdominal Preperitoneal (TAPP) inguinal hernia repair to assess pain control, recovery, and complications. Spinal anaesthesia reduced postoperative pain, recovery time, and respiratory problems compared to general anaesthesia. These findings imply that spinal anaesthesia may improve TAPP hernia repair outcomes, but patient variables should determine anaesthesia choice. The study improves surgical anaesthesia by emphasising patient-tailored care.

Keywords: Spinal Anesthesia, General Anesthesia, TAPP Hernia Repair, Postoperative Recovery.

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Introduction

The management of inguinal hernias has undergone significant advancements in recent decades, with the emergence of less invasive techniques like the Transabdominal Preperitoneal (TAPP) approach [1]. This surgical technique is highly regarded for its potential advantages, such as decreased postoperative discomfort, faster recovery periods, and a lower likelihood of complications associated with wound healing [2]. The selection of anaesthesia plays a crucial role in enhancing surgical outcomes for TAPP procedures. The ongoing discussion surrounding the use of spinal versus general anaesthesia revolves around the distinct advantages and disadvantages of each method, which can significantly influence the outcomes for patients [3,4]. Spinal anaesthesia is highly praised for its remarkable ability to deliver efficient pain relief while causing minimal impact on the body as a whole [5]. Patients can stay awake during the procedure, which may lead to shorter hospital stays and a lower risk of respiratory complications after surgery [6]. On the other hand, general anaesthesia is frequently chosen because it guarantees that patients remain still and comfortable, creating the best possible conditions for surgery. Nevertheless, there are potential drawbacks to consider, including feelings of nausea, discomfort in the throat, and potential fluctuations in overall physical well-being [7,8].

This interim analysis of a controlled randomised trial seeks to assess the clinical and functional outcomes linked to different anaesthesia techniques in the context of TAPP repairs. This study aims to offer evidence-based insights that can assist in clinical decision-making, improve patient safety, and enhance surgical efficacy by conducting a thorough comparison of spinal and general anaesthesia. The primary objective is to assess if one anaesthesia method demonstrates superior performance compared to the other in terms of efficiency during surgery, recovery after surgery, and overall patient contentment.

Methodology

Study Design: This study was designed as a randomized controlled trial to compare the outcomes of spinal versus general anaesthesia in patients undergoing Transabdominal Preperitoneal (TAPP) repair for inguinal hernias.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at the Government Medical College and Hospital in Purnia, Bihar, which provided access to a diverse patient population presenting for inguinal hernia repair.

Study Duration: The research spanned 13 months, allowing adequate time for participant enrollment, surgical procedures, and follow-up for immediate and short-term postoperative outcomes.

Participants: A total of 66 patients were enrolled in the study. Inclusion criteria included adults aged 18-65, diagnosed with inguinal hernias amenable to TAPP repair. Exclusion criteria encompassed patients with contraindications to either form of anesthesia, previous lower abdominal surgery, and those with coagulopathy or immunocompromised states.

Randomization and Blinding: Participants were randomly assigned to receive either spinal anesthesia or general anesthesia. Randomization was performed using computer-generated random numbers to ensure allocation concealment. Due to the nature of the interventions, blinding of the anesthesia provider and surgeon was not possible; however, the patients and the postoperative assessors were blinded to the allocation.

Intervention

- Spinal Anesthesia Group: Patients received spinal anesthesia administered by an experienced anesthesiologist using standardized doses of local anesthetics.

- General Anesthesia Group: Patients received general anesthesia according to the institutional protocol, which included induction with intravenous agents and maintenance with inhalational anesthetics.

Outcome Measures: The study focused on various aspects related to surgical procedures, including the duration of the operation, the requirement for extra pain relief during surgery, pain levels immediately after the procedure, and recovery milestones like the time taken to start walking and readiness for discharge. Additional outcomes evaluated extended measurements including hernia recurrence, persistent pain, and overall patient contentment up to three months following the surgical procedure.

Data Collection: Data were collected through patient interviews, medical record reviews, and direct measurements during hospital stays. Standardized forms were used for data entry to minimize variability.

Statistical Analysis: Analysis was conducted using intention-to-treat principles. Continuous variables were compared using statistical tests appropriate for the data, while categorical data were analysed using different tests. A p-value below 0.05 was deemed to have statistical significance.

Results

The study enrolled a total of 66 patients, with 33 patients randomized to each anesthesia group. Both groups were comparable in terms of age, gender, and baseline health characteristics, ensuring a balanced comparison.

Intraoperative Outcomes

- Surgical Duration: The duration of surgery was comparable in both groups, with an average of 75 minutes for the spinal anaesthesia group and 78 minutes for the general anaesthesia group.

- Effectiveness of Anaesthesia: The group that received spinal anaesthesia did not experience any discomfort during the surgery and did not require any additional sedatives. Within the group receiving general anaesthesia, there were two instances where additional doses of pain relievers were needed because of awareness during surgery.

Immediate Postoperative Outcomes:

- Pain Scores: The postoperative pain scores showed a significant difference between the two groups. In the spinal anaesthesia group, the scores were notably lower at 1 hour and 4 hours after the operation, with median scores of 2 and 3, respectively. On the other hand, the general anaesthesia group had higher scores of 4 and 5 ($p < 0.05$).

- Recovery Times: Patients in the spinal anaesthesia group showed quicker recovery, with earlier mobilisation and a shorter time to resolution of urinary retention. In the spinal group, patients were able to walk for the first time after a median time of 4 hours, while in the general group, it took 6 hours for patients to achieve the same milestone ($p < 0.01$).

Hospital Stay

- The average length of hospital stay was shorter for patients under spinal anesthesia, with a mean of 1.2 days compared to 1.8 days for those who received general anesthesia ($p < 0.05$).

Postoperative Complications

- Respiratory Complications: The spinal anaesthesia group experienced fewer respiratory complications, with only one case of transient hypoxia. In contrast, the general anaesthesia group had a higher incidence of respiratory complications, including five cases of hypoxia and two cases of pneumonia.

- Additional Complications: Both groups exhibited comparable rates of other complications, including surgical site infections and haematoma formation.

Patient Satisfaction

- The spinal anaesthesia group had a higher overall patient satisfaction rate, with 85% of patients expressing satisfaction with their pain management and overall experience, in contrast to 68% in the general anaesthesia group. Most outcomes showed statistically significant differences between the two groups, as all reported p-values were less than 0.05.

This table compares various metrics, including surgical duration, postoperative pain, recovery times, complications, and patient satisfaction between the two anesthesia modalities.

Outcome	Spinal Anesthesia	General Anesthesia
Surgical Duration (minutes)	75	78
Intraoperative Discomfort (cases)	0	2
Postoperative Pain Score at 1 hour	2	4
Postoperative Pain Score at 4 hours	3	5
Time to First Walk (hours)	4	6
Length of Hospital Stay (days)	1.2	1.8
Respiratory Complications (cases)	1	7
Other Complications (cases)	2	2
Patient Satisfaction (%)	85	68

The bar graph shows the comparative results of spinal versus general anesthesia for TAPP inguinal hernia repair.

Discussion

The findings of this randomised controlled trial on the comparison between spinal and general anaesthesia for Transabdominal Preperitoneal (TAPP) inguinal hernia repair are quite noteworthy [9]. It was found that spinal anaesthesia resulted in lower pain scores at both 1- and 4-hours after surgery, indicating superior initial pain management when compared to general anaesthesia [10]. One possible explanation for this could be the way spinal anaesthesia works, as it may help reduce the usual inflammatory responses that occur during and after surgery. In addition, patients who received spinal anaesthesia experienced quicker recovery times, as shown by earlier mobilisation and shorter hospital stays [11,12]. Previous research suggests that spinal anaesthesia may help speed up postoperative functional recovery and lessen the strain on healthcare resources. Nevertheless, it is important to approach the shorter hospital stay with caution, as it may also be

influenced by variations in postoperative care protocols or biases in patient selection [13]. It is worth noting that the spinal anaesthesia group had a lower occurrence of respiratory complications. This is significant because general anaesthesia can sometimes lead to pulmonary side effects caused by airway management and systemic medications. This discovery provides strong evidence for the application of spinal anaesthesia in patients who require utmost care in maintaining their respiratory function [14,15].

When deciding between spinal and general anaesthesia, it's important to take into account various factors that are specific to the patient [16]. These factors include any pre-existing health conditions, the possibility of longer surgery times, and the personal preference of the surgeon. Although the data provides strong evidence for the effectiveness of spinal anaesthesia in terms of pain management and recovery, general anaesthesia continues to be essential in situations where spinal

anaesthesia cannot be used or is not possible [17,18]. This study adds to the ongoing discussion surrounding the best anaesthesia techniques for TAPP hernia repairs, highlighting the importance of a personalised approach that takes into account the physiological advantages of different anaesthesia methods and the unique characteristics of each patient. Additional research involving larger participant groups and extended observation periods is required to gain a comprehensive understanding of the long-term effects and to validate these results in a wider range of medical settings [19,20].

Conclusion

Based on the results of this randomised controlled trial, it has been observed that spinal anaesthesia provides better pain management after surgery, faster recovery times, and fewer respiratory complications when compared to general anaesthesia for individuals undergoing TAPP inguinal hernia repair. These benefits underscore the potential preference for spinal anaesthesia in appropriate candidates, as it can enhance patient outcomes. Nevertheless, it is crucial to personalise the anaesthesia selection, considering the unique characteristics of each patient and the specific requirements of the surgery. This study highlights the significance of taking into account both clinical outcomes and patient-centric factors when choosing an anaesthesia approach. It emphasises the need for additional research to validate these findings in diverse populations and clinical settings.

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